

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that paper entitled 'Nebulization Therapy for Lung Cancer' author by Shukla Maitri Jayeshkumar, Patel Yashvi, Mr. Bhavin Bhimani, Mr. Ghanshyam Patel, Mr. Jaimin Patel, Dr. Upendra Patel has been published in **Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology (RJPT)** (print ISSN 0974-3618, online ISSN 0974-360X), February 2019, Vol. 12, Issue 2, pages 920-934.

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Nebulization Therapy for Lung Cancer

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ABSTRACT:

Cancer is the most leading cause of death worldwide. It is the disease in which abnormal cells divide uncontrollably and destroy body's tissue. Cancer, also called malignancy, is the spread of abnormal cells that can infiltrate the normal body tissues. There are more than 100 types of cancer including lung cancer, blood cancer, breast cancer, colon cancer, prostate cancer, skin cancer, lymphoma etc. Among these, Lung cancer is one of the most common and serious cancers in the world. It is the uncontrollable growth of abnormal cells that start off in one or both the lungs, usually in the cells that line the air passages. The anticancer drugs used not only affect the tumor cells but even the normal body cells. Treating lung cancer using various methods such as radiations, chemotherapy, surgery till now, has various side effects of hair loss, heart problems, kidney and liver problems, fatigue, nausea, vomiting etc. Therefore, there arises a need of some targeted drug delivery system which minimizes the side effects of the drug on lungs and acts only at the tumor site. One such targeted drug delivery system is "Nebulization Chemotherapy". It is the inhalation therapy through which the anticancer drug reaches to the tumor site in lungs, kills the cancerous cells without affecting the normal body cells and excretes out of the body. Here, the anticancer drug is inhaled as aerosols so that the drug can easily accumulate in the alveoli in lung. The inhaler therapy using nebulizer commonly used for local and systemic drug delivery of drug through lungs is promising now days. Inhalation therapy using nebulizer has several advantages like large dose can be administered, quick action, easy and convenient administration of the drug. Nebulizer uses oxygen, compressed air or ultrasonic powder to break up medical solutions and suspensions into small aerosol droplet called mists that can be directly inhaled from the mouthpiece of the device. Thus, the near future needs nebulization chemotherapy as the targeted drug delivery system as the new cure of lung cancer. It would be a breakthrough innovation in the treatment of lung cancer.

KEYWORDS: Lung, cancer, nebulization, chemotherapy, aerosols, targeted drug delivery.

INTRODUCTION TO CANCER:

Every year an estimated 11 million people are diagnosed with cancer (excluding skin cancers) and nearly 7 million people are recorded as dying from cancer. Cancer is increasing at rates faster than the increase in global population. (1)

Cancer is a disease which occurs when changes in a group of normal cells within the body lead to uncontrolled growth causing a lump called a tumor. If left untreated, tumors can grow and lymphatic systems, and can affect the digestive, nervous and circulatory systems. Tumors can and spread into the surrounding

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normal tissue, or to other parts of the body via the bloodstream be malignant or benign. (2)

Cancer is the second leading cause of death in the world after cardiovascular diseases. Half of men and one third of women in the United States will develop cancer during their lifetimes. Today, millions of cancer people extend their life due to early identification and treatment. Cancer is not a new disease and has afflicted people throughout the world. The word cancer came from a Greek words karkinos to describe carcinoma tumors by a physician Hippocrates (460–370 B.C), but he was not the first to discover this disease. Some of the earliest evidence of human bone cancer was found in mummies in ancient Egypt and in ancient manuscripts dates about 1600 B.C.(3)

TYPES OF CANCER:

Figure 1- Types of cancer

CAUSES OF CANCER:

Cancer-causing substances (carcinogens):

Genes are coded messages inside a cell that tell it how to behave (i.e. which proteins to make). Mutation or changes to the gene, such as damage or loss, can alter how that cell behaves. Mutation may mean that too much protein is made, or that protein is not made at all. Significantly, there needs to be a number of genetic mutations within a cell before it becomes cancerous. Something that damages a cell, changing its behavior and makes it more likely to be cancerous is called a 'carcinogen'.(4) The proportion of agents causing cancer is mentioned in figure2.

Age:

Many types of cancer become more prevalent with age. The longer people live, the more exposure there is to carcinogens and the more time there is for genetic changes or mutations to occur within their cells.(4)

Genetics:

Some people are unfortunately born with a genetically inherited high risk for a specific cancer ('genetic predisposition'). When women that carry the BRCA 1 and BRCA 2 breast cancer genes have a higher predisposition to developing this form of cancer than women with a normal breast cancer risk. So although women with one of these genes are individually more likely to develop breast cancer, most cases are not caused by a high risk inherited gene fault.(4)The mortality rates for different types of cancer are mentioned in table-1

The immune system:

People who have weakened immune systems are at more risk of cancer. This includes people who have had organ transplants and take drugs to suppress their immune systems to stop organ rejection, people who have HIV or AIDS, or other medical conditions which reduce their immunity to disease. Certain lifestyles and environmental factors are also known to cause mutations. (4)

Bodyweight, diet and physical activity:

Cancer experts estimate that maintaining a healthy bodyweight, making changes to our diet and taking regular physical activity could prevent about one in three deaths from cancer. Many people eat too much red and processed meat and not enough fresh fruit and vegetables. This type of diet is known to increase the risk of cancer.(4)

Overweight or obesity:

'Obese' means being more than about 25% overweight. Overweight or obese people have an increased risk of bowel and pancreatic cancer, probably due to a tendency towards higher insulin levels. Obesity can also increase the risk of cancer of the food pipe (oesophageal cancer), kidney and gallbladder cancer, as well as breast or womb (uterine) cancer in women.

Figure-2 Causes of cancer

Table1- Mortality rates due to different types of cancer

Cancer positively associated with smoking	Sex	Standardizing mortality per 100 years	Standardizing mortality per 100 years	Relative risk	Absolute excess risk per 1000000 years	Attributable proportion (%)*
		Life-long nonsmokers	Current cigarette smokers			
Lung cancer	Male	24	537	22.4	513	87
	female	18	213	11.9	195	77
Cancer on the upper respiratory sites	male	1	27	24.5	26	89
	female	2	10	5.6	8	58
Cancer of bladder and other urinary organs	male	18	53	2.9	35	36
	female	8	21	2.6	13	32
Pancreatic cancer	male	18	38	2.1	20	25
	female	16	37	2.3	21	29
Oesophageal cancer	male	9	68	7.6	59	66
	female	4	41	10.3	37	74
Kidney cancer	male	8	23	3	15	37
	female	6	8	1.4	2	11

WHAT IS LUNG CANCER?

Lung cancer is one of the most common cancers in the world, accounting for 1.8 million new cases each year. It is also the biggest cancer killer, with incidence rates higher in men than women. There are particularly high prevalence rates seen in Central, Eastern and Southern Europe, Northern America and Eastern Asia.(5)

- 1.6 million deaths each year are attributable to lung cancer.
- Overall, lung cancer is the cause of 19% of all cancer deaths.
- 13% of all new cases of cancer are lung cancers.

More than two-thirds of lung cancers are diagnosed at a late stage and only 10-15% of lung cancer patients survive for at least five years after diagnosis. Lung cancer is the term used to describe the growth of abnormal cells lining the air passages inside the lung tissue. These cells divide and grow more rapidly than normal cells and combine to form a cluster, or tumor.(5)

CAUSES OF LUNG CANCER:

Figure-3 risk factors causing lung cancer

Tobacco smoking:

Tobacco smoking is the main known cause of human cancer-related death worldwide. Smoking most

commonly causes lung cancer. For a smoker, lung cancer risk is related to the parameters of tobacco smoking in accordance with the basic principles of chemical carcinogenesis: risk is determined by the dose of carcinogen, the duration of administration and the intensity of exposure.(6) The risk factors causing cancer are mentioned in figure 3.

The risk is also proportional to the duration of smoking. hence, the annual death rate from lung cancer among 55-64 year-olds who smoked 21-39 cigarettes daily is about three times higher for those who started smoking at age 15 than for those who started at age 25. Intensity of exposure to tobacco smoke is determined by the smoking device used (cigarette, cigar, pipe, hookah, etc.). Similarly, filtered and low-tar cigarettes entail a lower risk for most tobacco-related cancers than unfiltered and high-tar cigarettes. (6)

All smoking tobacco products entail a carcinogenic. In the USA, Europe and Japan, 83-92% of lung cancer in men and 57-80% of lung cancer in women is tobacco-related. Most data involve cigarette smoking but, for example, cigar and pipe smoking present a greater risk for cancer of the oral cavity than does cigarette smoking.(7)

Alcohol consumption:

Alcohol drinking and tobacco smoking show a synergistic interaction in the etiology of cancers of the oral cavity, pharynx, larynx and esophagus; the risk of cancer for heavy consumers of both products relative to that for subjects who neither smoke nor drink is higher than the product of the risks attributable respectively to heavy drinking and heavy smoking separately.(8). Very heavy drinkers (e.g. alcoholics), among whom alcohol can be the source of up to 30% of total calorie intake, tend to have a diet poor in fruit and vegetables, which may further enhance their risk of developing these cancers.(9)

For all cancers caused by drinking alcohol, the risk of cancer is a linear function of the level of consumption,

up to an intake of about 80 g/day (one litre of wine, a quarter of a litre of spirits), above which level the dose-response relationship is less clearly defined.(10). The risk of head and neck cancer is 5-10 times higher in heavy drinkers than in abstainers, the carcinogenic effect of alcohol appearing to be more potent in the oral cavity, pharynx and oesophagus and weaker in the larynx.(11)

Hazardous materials:

Cancer of the lung can be caused by exposure to inorganic arsenic in mining and copper smelting. An increased incidence of lung cancer has also been recorded among workers in chromate producing industries and among chromium platers and chromium alloy workers. The below mentioned table-2 describes the hazardous materials causing cancer. Increased risk is predominantly associated with hexavalent chromium compounds. Nickel refining carries a carcinogenic risk in processes involving nickel (sub)sulfides, oxides and soluble nickel salts.(12). Work in iron and steel founding is also associated with an elevated risk of lung cancer; in addition to coal related emissions, such work may involve exposure to silica, metal fumes and formaldehyde.(13) Hazardous material asbestos if given in figure 4.

Figure 4- Asbestos causing lung cancer

Environmental pollution:

Ambient air pollution has been implicated as a cause of various health problems, including cancer, and in particular as a cause of lung cancer. It is possible to attribute at least some carcinogenic risk to particular atmospheric pollutants, including benzo[a]pyrene, benzene, some metals, particulate matter (especially fine particles) in general, and possibly ozone.(14). Lung cancer rates were higher in urban areas and, in some studies, were correlated with levels of specific pollutants such as benzo[a]pyrene, metals and particulate matter, or with mutagenicity of particulate extracts in bacterial assay systems.

Localized air pollution may be a hazard in petroleum refineries, metal manufacturing plants, iron foundries, incinerator plants and smelters.(15) Three determinants of indoor air pollution have been studied: heating fuel, cooking fuel and fumes from frying oils. In circumstances of high exposure, more than 50% of cases

of lung cancer among women can be attributed to indoor air pollution.(16)

Radiation:

Medical exposures occur both in the diagnosis (e.g. radiography) of diseases and injuries and in the treatment (e.g. radiotherapy) of cancer and of some benign diseases. Manmade sources of radiation can cause cancer and are a risk for workers. The main risk is however, prolonged and unprotected exposure to ultraviolet radiations from the sun which can lead to melanoma and skin malignancies.(17)

Table2- Hazardous material causing lung cancer

Agent	Cancer site/ cancer
Arsenic and arsenic compounds	Lung
Asbestos	Lung
Beryllium and beryllium compounds	Lung
Bis(chloromethyl) ether	Lung
Cadmium and cadmium compounds	Lung
Chloromethyl methyl ether	Lung
Chromium compounds	Lung, nasal compounds
Coal tar pitches	Lung
Mustard gas	Pharynx, lung
Nickel compounds	Nasal cavity, lung
Silica, crystalline	Lung
Soots	Lung
Strong inorganic acid mist containing sulphuric acid	Larynx, lung
Talc containing asbestiform fibers	Lung
Benz(a)anthracene	Lung
Benzo(a)pyrene	Lung
Chlorinated toluenes	Lung
Aluminum production	Lung
coal gasification	Lung
Coke production	Lung
Haemetite mining(underground)with exposure to radon	Lung
Iron and steel founding	Lung
Painter(construction industry)	Lung
Non arsenic insecticides	Lung
Diesel engine exhaust	Lung

Fair skinned people, those with lot of moles or who have a relative who has had melanoma or nonmelanoma skin cancer, are at highest risk occupational exposure to ionizing radiation occurs in a number of jobs, including the nuclear industry and medicine. Airline pilots and crew are exposed to lung cancer.(18) The radiating agents causing cancer are mentioned in table 3.

Table 3- Radiating agents causing lung cancer

Radiating agents causing cancer	Location
Radon-222 and its decay product	lung
Plutonium-239 and its decay product	lung

TYPES OF LUNG CANCER:

Lung cancer is not just one disease. There are two main types of lung cancer. Other types are mentioned in figure 5.

Figure5- Types of lung cancer

NON-SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER (NSCLC) AND ITS TYPES:

NSCLC is the most common form of lung cancer, comprising of 80-85% of lung cancer cases. NSCLC can be further divided into several different subtypes which are determined by the types of cells and the location of the tumor. Each subtype needs to be treated differently. The most common subtypes are-

- 1-Adenocarcinoma
- 2-Squamous cell carcinoma
- 3-Large cell carcinoma
- 4-Carcinoid tumors
- 5-other cancers

Adenocarcinoma:

Adenocarcinoma cells have a glandular appearance. Most of these tumors produce a thick fluid called mucin. The incidence of adenocarcinoma has increased over the past three decades. Scientists are not certain why this has occurred, but some influences may include changes in smoking habits, dietary patterns, environmental factors, and occupational factors. Some characteristics of adenocarcinoma are listed below.(19)

- Adenocarcinoma accounts for approximately 40% of all lung cancers in the United States, and approximately 55% of NSCLCs.
- Variants of adenocarcinoma include acinar adenocarcinoma, papillary adenocarcinoma, bronchioloalveolar adenocarcinoma, and other mixed subtypes.
- Adenocarcinoma is the most common form of lung cancer in women and people who have never smoked. This form of lung cancer is also the most common type seen in people less than age 50.
- Tumors are most often in the outer regions of the lungs.

- Adenocarcinomas are the most common form of lung cancer associated with scarring of the lung tissue.
- A subtype of adenocarcinoma called bronchioloalveolar adenocarcinoma (BABAC) has a more favorable prognosis than other forms of NSCLC.(19)

Squamous cell carcinoma (25-40% of NSCLC):

It develops in the squamous cells that line the airways and tends to spread locally. It is often caused by smoking and has limited treatment options. Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) is also known as epidermoid carcinoma. This form of NSCLC has decreased in frequency over the past three decades, but is still the most common form of lung cancer among men who are current or former smokers. Squamous cells are large, flat cells. These tumors often produce a substance called keratin, which can be seen under the microscope. Some features of SCC are listed below.(19)

- SCC accounts for approximately 25-30% of lung cancer in the United States.
- Variants of SCC include papillary SCC, clear cell SCC, small cell SCC, and basaloid SCC
- SCC occurs most frequently in men and in people over age 65 of both sexes.
- SCC usually starts in one of the larger airways. Therefore, these tumors tend to be located in the central area of the lung.
- There is a tendency for SCC to metastasize somewhat later than other forms of NSCLC.
- SCC tumors often invade neighboring structures.
- SCC is strongly associated with tobacco smoking.(19)

Large cell carcinoma (3-5% of NSCLC):

It named after the large, rounded cells that are seen when examined microscopically. It is sometimes known as 'undifferentiated carcinoma' and has a high tendency to spread to other parts of the body. The cells of large cell carcinoma (LCC) are the largest of the various types of NSCLC. The cells are generally highly undifferentiated or immature in appearance. Some experts believe these tumors represent adenocarcinomas or squamous cell carcinomas that are so undifferentiated as to be unrecognizable. Some characteristics of large cell carcinoma are(19)

- LCC accounts for 10-15% of lung cancers in the United States.
- There are several variants of large cell carcinoma including clear cell LCC, basaloid LCC, lymphoepithelioma-like carcinoma, and large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma.
- This form of NSCLC can occur in any part of the lung.
- The prognosis for large cell carcinoma is generally less favorable than for other forms of NSCLC. (19)

Other cancers:

There are other types of non-epithelial cancers that arise in the lungs. Examples of these cancers include carcinoid tumors, malignant pleural mesotheliomas, fibrosarcoma, and leiomyosarcomas. The lungs are also a frequent location for metastatic tumors from other locations in the body.(19)

Carcinoid Tumors:

Carcinoid tumors are cancers that arise from neuroendocrine cells. Neuroendocrine cells are specialized nerve cells that produce hormones. The hormones from neuroendocrine cells are released into the blood stream and travel to target cells throughout the body. The hormones may stimulate, inhibit, or maintain the function of their target cells. Malignant Pleural Mesothelioma. Malignant pleural mesothelioma (MPM) is cancer arising from the covering of the lung and chest wall, not the lung itself. The covering on the surface of the lungs is called the visceral pleura. The covering on the inside of the chest wall is called the parietal pleura. There are other pleural surfaces in the body, but about 75% of malignant mesotheliomas occur in the pleura of the lungs.(19)

SMALL CELL LUNG CANCER (SCLC):

About 15% of all lung cancers are small cell lung cancer. In this type, the cancerous cells are small cells in which the nucleus (the control centre of cells) dominates.

As the name implies, the cancerous epithelial cells of SCLC are abnormally small. Their appearance led to the term oat cell carcinoma to describe SCLC because the cells resemble oat grains. SCLC is also sometimes called small cell undifferentiated carcinoma. Carcinoma is a generic term referring to any malignant tumor that comes from epithelial cells. SCLC cells are sometimes spindle-shaped or polygonal (multisided). Some characteristics of SCLC are(19)

- There is a strong relationship between SCLC and tobacco smoking. Only about 1% of SCLC occurs in people who have never smoked.
- SCLC typically grows more quickly than NSCLC does. It tends to spread to lymph nodes and metastasize to other organs early in the disease process.
- SCLC often occurs in one of the larger airways. Therefore, SCLC tumors are often located near the center of the lung.(19)

STAGES OF LUNG CANCER:

Stages of Lung Cancer

Figure 6 – Stages of lung cancer

PRESENT TREATMENTS:

Surgery:

People with early stage NSCLC (stage I and stage II) will generally have surgery to remove the tumor. How much of the lung is removed depends on the location of the cancer, its size, your general wellbeing and fitness, as well as your lung function.(20)

Removing lymph nodes:

During surgery, nearby lymph nodes will also be removed to see whether the cancer has spread. Knowing if the cancer has spread to the lymph nodes also helps the doctors decide whether you need further treatment with chemotherapy or radiotherapy.(21)

Radiotherapy:

Radiotherapy uses x-rays to kill or damage cancer cells. It can be used to treat all types of lung cancer. It may be offered on its own or in combination with surgery or chemotherapy. Radiotherapy can be used: to treat an early stage lung cancer if you are unable to have surgery to treat locally advanced (stage III) NSCLC or stages I-III SCLC after surgery if the mediastinal lymph nodes contained cancer, to reduce the risk of the cancer coming back in the mediastinum as palliative treatment to treat cancer that has spread to other organs, such as the brain or bones, and is causing symptoms as palliative treatment to relieve pain and improve quality of life or extend your life.(22)

Chemotherapy:

Chemotherapy is the treatment of cancer with anti-cancer (cytotoxic) drugs. The aim is to destroy cancer cells while causing the least possible damage to normal, healthy cells. Chemotherapy can be used at different times, including: before surgery (neo-adjuvant chemotherapy), to try to shrink the cancer and make the operation easier before radiotherapy or during radiotherapy (chemoradiotherapy or chemoradiation), to make radiotherapy more effective after surgery (adjuvant chemotherapy), to reduce the risk of the cancer. Chemotherapy is usually delivered through an intravenous drip. Each chemotherapy treatment is called a cycle and is followed by a rest period to give your body time to recover. The number of treatments you have will depend on the type of lung cancer you have and how well your body is coping with the side effects.(23)

Hormonal therapy:

In 1878 Thomas Beatson discovered that the breasts of rabbits stopped producing milk after he removed ovaries. Later scientists identified that dramatic regression of metastatic prostate cancer following removal of the testes. Now new classes of drugs (aromatase inhibitors, LHRH analogs) are being used to treat prostate and breast cancers. How hormones influence growth of cancer has guided progress in developing as well as reducing the risk of breast and prostate cancers.(24)

Adjuvant therapy:

It is the use of chemotherapy after surgery to destroy the few remaining cancer cells in the body. Adjuvant therapy was used in colon and testis cancers.

Immunotherapy:

Use of biological agents that mimic some of the natural signals that body uses to control tumor growth is called immunotherapy. These natural biological agents can now be produced in the laboratory including interferons,

interleukins, cytokines, endogenous angioinhibitors and antigens. In 1990s scientists produced therapeutic monoclonal antibodies rituximab and trastuzumab that specifically targeted lymphoma and breast cancer cells. At present scientists are developing vaccines to boost the body's immune response against cancer cells.(25)

NEBULISATION FOR LUNG CANCER:

Regional drug delivery has been an approach used clinical oncology for a few decades. In this way, it is assumed to improve the therapeutic efficacy of the antineoplastic agent by delivering relatively high concentrations locally at the tumorsite while minimizing systemic toxicity.(26)

The inhaler therapy using nebulizer is commonly used for local and systemic drug delivery of drug, through lung is promising now days. Nebulization therapy using nebulizer having several advantages large dose can be administered, quick action, easy and convenient to patient to administer the drug. Nebulizer formulations are known as Nebulization suspension or solution, which consists of drug dispersed or solubilised in aqueous based formulation containing other excipients.(27)

Nebulization therapy has played a vital role in the relieving respiratory diseases and lung cancer. Such pulmonary drug delivery compositions are designed to be delivered by Nebulization by the patient so that the active drug within the dispersion can reach the lung. It has been found that certain drugs given by pulmonary route are readily absorbed through the alveolar region directly into blood circulation. Pulmonary route possesses many advantages over other routes of administration for the treatment of specific disease states, particularly lung associated large protein molecules which degrade in the gastrointestinal conditions and are eliminated by the first pass metabolism in the liver can be delivered via the pulmonary route if deposited in the respiratory zone of the lungs.(28)

INTRODUCTION TO NEBULIZATION:

The word "nebulizer" (from the Latin "nebula", mist) was first used in 1872 and was defined in 1874 as "an instrument for converting liquid drugs into a wet mist. Nebulization therapy has played a pivotal role in the vistas of pulmonary drug delivery since ancient times, as a way of relieving respiratory diseases. Drug delivery by the Nebulization route is a rapidly developing and challenging aspect of pharmaceutical product development. In general, there are three types of devices commonly employed for pulmonary drug administration such as metered dose inhalers (MDIs), dry powder inhalers (DPIs) and nebulizers MDIs contain the drug in

suspension, emulsion or solution form to which a propellant has been added. When the device is activated, a metered dose is released at high velocity which requires a simultaneous Nebulization by the patient whereas DPIs are passively actuated, in which they utilize the respiratory intake of air by the patient to entrain and disintegrate the drug, which is in the form of dry powder particles. Among these, the nebulizers are preferred over the other aerosol generating devices because some patients cannot master the correct use of MDIs or DPIs, and some drugs for Nebulization are only available in solution form.(29) Figure 7 shows deposition of anticancer drug as aerosols to the alveoli.

As these devices aerosolize drug solution into a wet mist that floats deeply into the patient's airways as they inhale. In only a short duration, breathing the wet mist can relax patient's bronchial muscles and soothe raw air ways. The aim of nebulizer therapy is to deliver a therapeutic dose of desired drug in the form of an aerosol of respirable particles with in a fairly short period of time usually 5-15 min. Various advantages of drug delivery directly to the airway include rapid onset of a therapeutic effect, reduced drug dose need and limitation of systemic side effects, far outweigh those of any enteral or parenteral route of administration.

ADVANTAGES

- Large dose of drug can be administered over multiple breaths.
- Can be used at any age group.
- Require no propellants that can damage the atmosphere.
- Ensures more efficient intrabronchial drug deposition. In emergency medicine used to treat acute bronchial asthma and acute exacerbations of COPD, frequently in combination with positive pressure ventilation.
- Easy to administer in a very simple manner.

DISADVANTAGES:

- Higher cost and size complications.
- Time consuming compared to MDI & DPI.
- Noisy.
- High maintenance requirements i.e. the equipment must be cleaned and sterilized on regular basis and the air filtered.
- Dependent on outside power sources, electricity.

Figure7-inhalation of drug in form of aerosols to alveoli

NEBULIZERS:

Because nebulizers historically have worked with any drug formulation designed for nebulization, regulatory agencies have had a tendency to classify them as medical devices for testing purposes. As a result, the regulatory approach has differed from that applied to other Nebulization products such as DPIs and MDIs, with no requirement for drug specific testing with nebulizers. But regulatory authorities around the world are increasingly linking the approval of formulation and device of nebulizers. Because these devices operate continuously once loaded and require little or no coordination on the part of the user, they have proven particularly suitable for weak, pediatric, or geriatric patients. Nebulizers enjoy wide use both in the home and in hospitals to deliver many different drugs.(30). Conventional nebulizer designs, however, have a number of disadvantages. For one thing, they either require a supply of compressed air to operate jet technology that atomizes the liquid, or they need a source of electricity for ultrasonic aerosolization, seriously limiting their portability. Other disadvantages associated with conventional devices include their relatively large size, weight, inefficiency, and inter-brand variability.

New mesh technology that forms droplets with a closely controlled particle size by pushing the formulation through a static or vibrating plate, mesh, or membrane addresses many of these issues and has led to the development of portable, silent, battery-operated devices with improved delivery characteristics. Two major factors affect drug delivery with nebulizers: usage time

and droplet size. Unlike other Nebulization devices, nebulizers provide continuous delivery instead of a pre-metered dose of drug. Once loaded and activated, a nebulizer operates with the user breathing normally so that the patient's breathing profile and usage time determine the amount of drug received. As with other Nebulization products, nebulizers must produce droplets small enough to penetrate into the lungs instead of depositing in the oropharynx, and droplets must be large enough to avoid being exhaled in order to ensure effective drug delivery. Since nebulizers convert therapeutic liquids into aerosol droplets for inhalation, the drug-nebulizer combination is particularly important because the physical properties of the formulation influence aerosolization behavior and therefore droplet size.

In most cases, delivery to the lungs requires a droplet size of around 1-5 μm , although, for deep lung penetration, particularly in children, the target upper limit may be lower, closer to 3 μm . In addition, performance can vary significantly from device to device, which is especially true as new nebulizer technology comes to market. While developing and marketing a nebulizer for delivery of a range of formulations remains possible, this approach is becoming less common. Health Canada and EMEA issued new guidance for Europe and Canada late in 2006, and the "Guideline on the Pharmaceutical Quality of Nebulization and Nasal Products" outlines a harmonized approach consistent with that used for other Nebulization products, specifying drug-device testing for the majority of products.

MECHANISM:

Figure 8- Mechanism of nebulization and aerosol deposition in lung

PARTS OF NEBULISER:

There are lots of models of nebulizer out there, and each one is a little different from the others. This general guide to nebulizer parts will give you a basic idea of what makes a nebulizer system function.(31) The representation of parts of nebulizer is shown in figure 9.

- **Nebulizer compressor:**
The compressor is the base of the system. It pumps air into the medication cup to create a breathable mist.
- **Nebulizer cup:**
This is the reservoir where measured liquid medication goes.
- **Tubing:**
The tubing delivers air from the compressor to the medication cup.
- **Tubing connectors:**
These connect the tubing to the compressor and nebulizer cup.
- **Mouthpiece/mask:**
This is the opening through which the mist is inhaled. Most nebulizer sets come with mouthpieces, but masks are available for those who find them more comfortable or who have trouble wrapping their lips around the mouthpiece.
- **Nebulizer mask:**
A nebulizer mask fits over the mouth and nose to deliver medication directly to the airways. Nebulizer treatments require a mask or mouthpiece. Masks come in different sizes.
- **Nebulizer filters:**
These should be changed regularly in order to ensure the air you're breathing in is clean and that normal air contaminants do not get into your nebulizers. Using your nebulizer without the proper, clean air filter will cause normal air particles and contaminants to ruin your compressor.

Figure 9- Parts of nebulizer

- **Rechargeable nebulizer battery pack:**
If you have a portable nebulizer, a battery pack will ensure that your nebulizer is ready for use at all times.
- **Replacement power adapter:**
Tabletop nebulizers need to be plugged in order to function.
- **Carrying case:**
A carrying case helps protect your investment and makes traveling with a nebulizer more convenient. Many have pockets to hold smaller parts like masks and mouthpieces.(30)

TYPES OF NEBULIZERS:

Traditional nebulizers can be broadly classified into three categories depending on their operating principle such as jet, ultrasonic and mesh nebulizers. The jet nebulizer uses compressed air to aerosolize the drug solutions, whereas the ultrasonic nebulizer uses energy from high frequency sound waves. Various types of nebulizers with its advantage and disadvantage are given in table 5.

Jet Nebulizers:

Jet nebulizers are widely used in pediatric and adult medical practice, for acute and domiciliary treatment of a variety of respiratory diseases. They are also known as 'atomizers' or 'pneumatic nebulizers'. These nebulizers require 2 to 10 L/min of pressurized gas to draw medication up through a capillary tube from the nebulizer reservoir in order to generate a wide range of particle sizes that are blasted into one or more baffles, which take larger particles out of suspension and return them to the reservoir. Figure 10 shows the jet nebulizer.

Jet nebulizers operate on the Bernoulli principle, use high velocity air flow through nozzle to draw liquid containing the drug side feed tubes into the nozzle region as a consequence of suction arising from the expansion of the jet at the nozzle orifice. The liquid immediately breaks up into aerosol droplets as it emanates from feed tubes due to the large kinetic energy of the air jet. Baffle is a standard component of a jet nebulizer which provides a surface for aerosolized droplets to impact and subsequently coalesce, thus draining back into the reservoir Jet nebulizers are divided into four categories

Table 5- Types of nebulizers with its advantage and disadvantage

Sr. No.	Nebulizers	Advantages	Disadvantages
1a)	Jet nebulizers with corrugated tubing	Cheap. Easy to use. Effective in delivering drugs that cannot be delivered with MDIs and DPIs.	Inefficient. Difficult to clean. Need compressed and additional tubing.
1b)	Breath-actuated & Breath enhanced jet nebulizers	Drug delivery only during inhalation. Easy to use. Less medication wasted. More efficient than JNs with 3 tubing.	Need sufficient flow to trigger drug delivery. Takes longer to deliver drug. Not ventilator-enabled. More expensive.
2)	Ultrasonic nebulizers	Easy to use. More efficient than jet nebulizers.	Large residual volume. Inability to aerosolize viscous solutions. Degradation of heat-sensitive materials.
3)	Mesh nebulizers	Fast, quiet, portable. Self-contained power source. Optimize particle size for specific drugs. More efficient than other nebulizers. Easy to use.	More expensive. Cleaning can be difficult. Medication dosage must be adjusted. Not compatible with viscous liquids or those that crystallize on drying.

(1) jet nebulizers with a corrugated tube. (2) jet nebulizers with a collection bag. (3) breath-enhanced jet nebulizers. (4) breath-actuated jet nebulizers.

Figure 10- Jet nebulizer

(1) Jet Nebulizers with a Corrugated Tube:

They are conventional constant output nebulizers that generate continuous aerosol during inspiration, expiration, and breath-hold. Although the corrugated tube attached to the jet nebulizer acts as a reservoir, there is still significant drug loss during expiration with this type of nebulizer. While jet nebulizers with a corrugated tube have several disadvantages, they are easy to use and have a good profile on patient compliance with treatment.

(2) Jet Nebulizers with a Collection Bag:

They are considered a dosimetric nebulizer that releases aerosol only during inhalation. Aerosols generated during expiration are stored in the collection bag and given to the patient with the next inspiration through a one-way valve that is located between the mouthpiece and the collection bag. The Circulaire (Westmed INC, Tucson, AZ) is an example of this type of nebulizer. The Circulaire decreases the amount of drug loss.(27)

(3) Breath-Enhanced Jet Nebulizers:

They release more aerosols during Nebulization through one-way valves in the mouthpiece. They generate aerosols using a negative pressure created by a patient's

inspiratory effort. PARI LC Plus, (PARI, Midlothian, VA) PARI LCD (PARI, Midlothian, VA), and Nebu Tech, (Salter Labs, Arvin, CA) are examples of breath-enhanced jet nebulizers. The efficiency of breath-enhanced nebulizers is better than jet nebulizers with corrugated tubing.

(4) Breath-Actuated Jet Nebulizers:

(BANs), like the Aero Eclipse (Monaghan/Trudell Medical International, London, Ontario, Canada), sense the patient's inspiratory flow and deliver aerosol only on inspiration. Therefore, these nebulizers decrease drug wastage during aerosol therapy but can increase treatment time. Since it generates aerosol in response to the patient's inspiratory maneuver, it has a low level of drug loss to the environment. The Aero Eclipse is easy to use and is associated with a lower occurrence of adverse events. Also, patients and respiratory therapists had greater satisfaction with the BAN in adult patient populations, compared to the jet nebulizer with a corrugated tube.

Ultrasonic Nebulizers:

Ultrasonic nebulizers incorporate a piezoelectric crystal vibrating at high frequencies (1-3 MHz) in order to produce aerosol. Ultrasonic nebulizers have many limitations compared to jet nebulizers. For instance, they have large residual volumes, an inability to aerosolize viscous solutions, and degradation of heat-sensitive materials. Therefore, they should not be used with suspensions and proteins. An ultrasonic nebulizer converts electrical energy to high-frequency ultrasonic waves. Small-volume ultrasonic nebulizers are commercially available for delivery of inhalable bronchodilators. Figure 11 shows the ultrasonic nebulizer and its arrangement.

Figure 11- Ultrasonic nebulizer and its arrangement

Mesh nebulizers:

The mesh nebulizer consists of a mesh or plate that has multiple apertures to produce an aerosol. These devices use a vibrating mesh or a vibrating horn. In the case of the vibrating mesh (eg, Aerogen Aeroneb, Nektar, San Carlos, California; eFlow, Pari, Richmond, Virginia), contraction and expansion of a vibrational element produces an upward and downward movement of a domed aperture plate. The aperture plate contains up to 1,000 tapered holes. The holes have a tapered shape with a larger cross-section on the liquid side and a smaller cross-section on the side the droplets emerge. The medication is placed in a reservoir above the domed aperture plate. Sound pressure is built up in the vicinity of the membrane, creating a pumping action that extrudes solution through the holes in the plate to produce an aerosol. The aerosol particle size and flow are determined by the exit diameter of the aperture holes. The size of the holes in the plate can be modified for specific clinical applications. Figure 12 shows the mechanism of jet nebulizer.

Figure 12- Mechanism of mesh nebulizer

SELECTION OF EXCIPIENTS:

In order to be effective, aerosolized chemotherapy must be delivered at a sufficient concentration to the target area. Aerosol particle size is one of the most important determinants of aerosol dose and distribution in the lungs. Aerosols with a mass median aerodynamic diameter (MMAD) of 5–10 μ m are mainly deposited in the oropharynx and large conducting airways. Particles of 1–5 μ m diameter are deposited in the small airways, and alveoli with 50% of 3 μ m-diameter particles being deposited in the alveolar region. The optimal site of deposition for aerosolized chemotherapy may be different for primary lung cancer located in or near the central airways, for bronchioloalveolar carcinoma located in the alveolar region and for multiple parenchymal metastases. Aerosol deposition in the target area can also be altered in the case of airway obstruction by the tumor or associated obstructive lung disease. The

inhaled drug may reach the tumor either via direct topical penetration for bronchogenic carcinomas located close to the airways or via the local blood supply (bronchial or pulmonary circulation) tumors located away from the airways.(31) Table 6 shows the use of various excipients.

It has been previously demonstrated that some physicochemical properties of drugs, ie, shape, charge, molecular weight, and aqueous solubility, determine the rate of diffusion through tissue. The penetration of a drug is also dependent on its deconstruction, which functions to remove free drug, thereby inhibiting further permeation. Water-soluble drugs distribute most readily in the extracellular matrix and thus diffuse efficiently around and between cells. In contrast, lipid-soluble drugs penetrate lipid membranes, and so can be transported through cells.(31)

Table- Role and use of various excipients to be used in the nebulisation therapy

Sr. No	Category	Role	Example of excipients used
1.	Isotonicity adjustment	Used to adjust the tonicity of the formulation	Sodium chloride, Dextrose
2.	pH adjustment	Used to adjust pH same to physiological conditions and maximize drug stability	Sodium hydroxide, hydrochloric acid sulphuric acid
3.	Purging	Purging used to reduce oxidation	Nitrogen
4.	Antimicrobial preservative	To avoid the microbial growth in the formulation	Benzalkonium chloride, ethanol, propylene glycol, Benzoyl Alcohol, chlorobutanol, Methyl paraben
5.	Buffer component	It gives the buffer capacity to formulation at desire pH	Sodium citrate, Sodium Phosphate, citric acid
6.	Surfactant	Increases suspendability and stability of suspension	Polysorbate 80, 20
7.	Cation chelating agent	Forms chelate with ions present in the formulation and increases the stability	Disodium EDTA
8.	Suspending Agents	Increases viscosity and suspendability of suspension	CMC, Na CMC
9.	Co-Solvent	Helps to improve solubility	Alcohol, PEG 400, Propylene Glycol
10.	Humactant	Used to maintain humidification in the formulation	Glycerin

CHARACTERIZATION OF NEBULIZER:

Ph:

For both Nebulization solution and suspension, the pH of the Formulation should be tested and an appropriate acceptance criterion established. Thus the stability can achieve by proper selection of pH of formulation. However, the pH of formulation should be (4.5-6.5) to prevent the sneezing.(32)

Osmolality:

For formulations containing an agent to control the tonicity or for products having a label claim regarding tonicity, the osmolality of the formulation should be tested and controlled at release. Some existing marketed products have reported osmolality in the range of 300-700 mOsmol/Kg.(32)

Impurities and Degradation Products:

The levels of impurities and degradation products should be determined by a validated analytical procedure or procedures. Acceptance criteria should be set for individual and total impurities and degradation products. All related impurities appearing at levels of 0.1 percent or greater should be specified according to ICH guideline for impurities. (32)

Preservatives and Stabilizing Excipients Assay:

If preservatives, antioxidants, chelating agents, or other stabilizing excipients (e.g., benzalkonium chloride, phenylethyl alcohol, edetate) are used in the formulation, there should be a specific assay for these components with associated acceptance criteria. Acceptance criteria for the chemical content of preservatives at the time of product release and through the product shelf life should be included in the drug product specification.(32)

Delivered Dose:

Delivered dose testing is carried out to determine the total amount of drug that the patient might be expected to receive during a treatment period. Two discrete

metrics are defined and measured: the active substance delivery rate and the total active substance delivered. Reflecting the mode of operation of nebulizers, delivered dose testing is carried out using well defined breathing profiles for specific patient types. The defined profiles for child, infant and neonate patients are based on significantly smaller volumes, higher breathing frequencies and different inhalation/exhalation ratios. To measure active substance delivery rate the output from the nebulizer is captured on a filter, under appropriate test conditions, over a specified time (typically 60 seconds). Longer test times are applied to provide sufficient mass (greater than the limit of quantification) for reliable analysis, where delivery rates are low. Replacing the filter and continuing the test until nebulization stops, because the reservoir is empty, enables calculation of the second metric – total active substance delivered. This is the total mass collected during steps 1 and 2 of the test. Mean Nebulization Time (MNT) and Mean Delivered Dose (MDD) determined at the labelled flow rate of 5.5 L/min through such time that mist is no longer coming out of the mouthpiece. (32)

Aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD):

Generally speaking a particle size range of < 5 microns is taken as being optimal for pulmonary deposition. Cascade impaction is the preferred method for APSD measurement because of its ability to provide well-resolved, drug specific particle size data in the size range of interest. Next generation impactor (NGI) instruments that operate under constant constant flow rate of 15 L/min used to determine APSD. Cooling of the NGI prior to testing is specified to decrease the evaporation of droplet. The aerodynamic size distribution may be characterized by the fine particle dose (FPD), mass median aerodynamic diameter (MMAD) and the geometric standard deviation (GSD). The MMAD is the most important parameter defining particle size, i.e. drug deposition. Theoretically, a monodisperse aerosol will exhibit a GSD of 1.0, in

practice however, a GSD of ≤ 1.22 is considered as monodisperse. (32)

Droplet size distribution:

The DSD of a nebulizer is a critical parameter, since it significantly influences the in vivo deposition of the drug in the lung. The droplet size is hereby mainly influenced by the formulation and the nebulizer device.

If a laser diffraction method is used, droplet distribution can be controlled in terms of ranges for D10, D50, D90, span $[(D90-D10)/D50]$, and percentage of droplets less than 10 μm . (32)

MARKETED FORMULATIONS:

Various marketed formulations as nebulisers used treatment of various diseases are as shown in table-7.

Table-7 marketed formulations for nebulizers used in various diseases

Sr. No.	Brand	Drug	Disease	Manufacturer
1.	Accuneh®	Albuterol Sulfate	Asthma	Dey Pharma
2.	Xopenex®	Levoalbuterol HCL	Asthma, COPD	Sunovion Pharma
3.	DuoNeb®	IpratropiumBromide,Albuterol Sulfate	Asthma, COPD	Dey Pharma
4.	Perforomist®	Formoterol Fumarate	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease	Dey Pharma
5.	SteriNeb®	Budesonide	Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis	Teva Pharmaceutical
6.	Pulmozyme®	Doranase Alpha	Cystic fibrosis	Genentech Inc.
7.	Caysten®	Aztreonam	Lower respiratory tract infection, urinary tract infection	Gilead Sci.

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